

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 44

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 44

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 44:0 For the choir director. A †Maskil of the sons of Korah.</p>	<p>לְמִנְצַח לְבְנֵי-קָרַח</p>
<p>Psa. 44:1 O God, we have heard with our ears, Our ^afathers have told us The ^bwork that You did in their days, In the ^cdays of old. ² You with Your own hand ^adrove out the nations; Then You ^bplanted them; You ^cafflicted the peoples, Then You ^dspread them abroad. ³ For by their own sword they ^adid not possess the land, And their own arm did not save them, But Your right hand and Your ^barm and the ^clight of Your presence, For You ^dfavor them.</p>	<p>מִשְׁכִּיל : ² אֱלֹהִים אֲבֹתֵינוּ וְאֲבוֹתֵינוּ שָׁמְעוּנוּ אֲבוֹתֵינוּ סִפְרוּ-לָנוּ פֶּעַל פֶּעַל פָּעַלְתָּ בְיָמֵיהֶם בְּיָמֵי קָדָם : ³ אַתָּה וַיְדָךְ גּוֹיִם הוֹרֵשְׁתָּ וְהַטַּעַם תָּרַע לְאֲמִים וְהַשְׁלַחְתָּם : ⁴ כִּי לֹא בַחֲרָבָם יָרְשׁוּ אֶרֶץ וַיִּזְרְעוּם לֹא- הוֹשִׁיעָה לָמוֹ כִּי-יִמְיָנָהּ וַיִּזְרְעוּ וְאוֹר פָּנֶיהָ כִּי רָצִיתָם : ⁵ אַתָּה-הוּא מַלְכֵּנוּ אֱלֹהִים צִוְּהָ יִשׁוּעוֹת יַעֲקֹב :</p>
<p>Psa. 44:4 You are ^amy King, O God; ^bCommand ¹victories for Jacob. ⁵ Through You we will ^apush back our adversaries; Through Your name we will ^btrample down those who rise up against us. ⁶ For I will ^anot trust in my bow, Nor will my sword save me. ⁷ But You ^ahave saved us from our adversaries, And You have ^bput to shame those who hate us. ⁸ In God we have ^aboasted all day long,</p>	<p>בְּךָ צָרֵינוּ נִגַּחַת בְּשִׁמְךָ נְבוֹים קָמֵינוּ : ⁷ כִּי לֹא בְּקִשְׁתִּי אֶבְטַח וְחִרְבִּי לֹא תוֹשִׁיעֵנִי : ⁸ כִּי הוֹשִׁיעָתָנוּ מִצָּרֵינוּ וּמִשְׁנֵאֵינוּ הִבִּישׁוֹתָ : בְּאֱלֹהִים הִלַּלְנוּ כָּל-הַיּוֹם וְשִׁמְךָ אֶלְעֹלָם נִזְכָּרָה סִלָּה : אֶרֶץ-זָנַחְתָּ וַתִּכְלִימֵנוּ וְלֹא-</p>

And we will ^bgive thanks to Your name forever. ¹Selah.

Psa. 44:9 Yet You ^ahave rejected *us* and brought us to ^bdishonor,

And ^cdo not go out with our armies.

¹⁰ You cause us to ^aturn back from the adversary;

And those who hate us ^bhave taken spoil for themselves.

¹¹ You give us as ^asheep ¹to be eaten
And have ^bscattered us among the nations.

¹² You ^asell Your people ¹cheaply,
And have not ²profited by their sale.

¹³ You make us a ^areproach to our neighbors,

A scoffing and a ^bderision to those around us.

¹⁴ You make us ^aa byword among the nations,

A ^{1b}laughingstock among the peoples.

¹⁵ All day long my dishonor is before me

And ¹my ^ahumiliation has overwhelmed me,

¹⁶ Because of the voice of him who ^areproaches and reviles,

Because of the presence of the ^benemy and the avenger.

Psa. 44:17 All this has come upon us, but we have ^anot forgotten You,

And we have not ^bdealt falsely with Your covenant.

¹⁸ Our heart has not ^aturned back,
And our steps ^bhave not deviated from Your way,

תִּצַּא בְּצַבָּאוֹתֵינוּ : ¹¹ תִּשְׁיבְנוּ

אֶחָד מִנֵּי-צָר וּמִשְׁנְאֵינוּ

שָׁסוּ לָמוֹ : ¹² תִּתְּנֵנוּ כְּצֹאן

מֵאֲכָל וּבְגוֹזִים זֵרִיתָנוּ : ¹³

תִּמְכֹּר-עַמְּךָ בְּלֹא-הוֹן וְלֹא-

רְבִית בְּמַחֲרֵיהֶם : ¹⁴

תִּשְׁימְנוּ חֶרֶף לְשִׁכְנֵינוּ לְעַג

וְקָלָם לְסִבִּיבוֹתֵינוּ : ¹⁵

תִּשְׁימְנוּ מִשָּׁל בְּגוֹזִים מְנוֹד-

רָאשׁ בַּל-אֲמִים : ¹⁶ כָּל-

הַיּוֹם כְּלַמְתִּי נִגְדִי וּבִשְׁת פְּנֵי

כְּסִתָּנִי : ¹⁷ מִקּוֹל מְחַרְךָ

וּמִגִּדְךָ מִפְּנֵי אוֹיֵב וּמִתְּנַקֵּם :

¹⁸ כָּל-זֹאת בָּאתָנוּ וְלֹא

שָׁכַחְנוּךָ וְלֹא-שָׁקַרְנוּ

בְּבְרִיתְךָ : ¹⁹ לֹא-נָסוּג אֶחָד

לִבְנוּ וַתֵּט אֲשֵׁרֵינוּ מִנֵּי

אֶרְחֶךָ : ²⁰ כִּי רַכִּיתָנוּ

בְּמִקּוֹם תְּנִים וַתִּכַּס עֲלֵינוּ

בְּצִלְמּוֹת : ²¹ אִם-שָׁכַחְנוּ שֵׁם

אֱלֹהֵינוּ וַנִּפְרָשׁ כַּפֵּינוּ לְאֵל

¹⁹ Yet You have ^acrushed us in a place of ^bjackals

And covered us with ^cthe shadow of death.

Psa. 44:20 If we had ^aforgotten the name of our God

Or extended our ¹hands to ^ba strange god,

²¹ Would not God ^afind this out?

For He knows the secrets of the heart.

²² But ^afor Your sake we are killed all day long;

We are considered as ^bsheep to be slaughtered.

²³ ^aArouse Yourself, why ^bdo You sleep, O Lord?

Awake, ^cdo not reject us forever.

²⁴ Why do You ^ahide Your face

And ^bforget our affliction and our oppression?

²⁵ For our ^asoul has sunk down into the dust;

Our body cleaves to the earth.

²⁶ ^aRise up, be our help,

And ^bredeem us for the sake of Your lovingkindness.

זָרָה : 22 הֲלֹא אֱלֹהִים יִתְקַרְר-

זֹאת כִּי-הוּא יִדַע תַּעֲלָמוֹת

לֵב : 23 כִּי-עָלִיף הַרְגָנוּ

כָּל-הַיּוֹם נְחַשְׁבָנוּ כְּצֹאן

טְבוּחָה : 24 עֹזְרָה אֲלֵמָה

תִּישָן אֲדֹנָי הַקִּיצָה אֶל-

תִּזְנַח לַנֶּצַח : 25 לְמָה-פְּנִיף

תִּסְתִיר תִּשְׁכַּח עֵינֵינוּ

וְלִחְצֵנוּ : 26 כִּי שָׁחָה לְעַפְר

נִבְשָנוּ דְבַקָה לְאָרֶץ בְּטִנְנוּ :

27 קוּמָה עֲזַרְתָה לָנוּ וּפְדֵנוּ

לְמַעַן חַסְדֶּךָ :

References

<p>Psalm 44:1 ^aEx 12:26, 27; Deut 6:20; Judg 6:13; Ps 78:3 ^bPs 78:12 ^cDeut 32:7; Ps 77:5; Is 51:9; 63:9</p> <p>Psalm 44:2 ^aJosh 3:10; Neh 9:24; Ps 78:55; 80:8 ^bEx 15:17; 2 Sam 7:10; Jer 24:6; Amos 9:15 ^cPs 135:10-12 ^dPs 80:9-11; Zech 2:6</p> <p>Psalm 44:3 ^aDeut 8:17, 18; Josh 24:12 ^bPs 77:15 ^cPs 4:6; 89:15 ^dDeut 4:37; 7:7, 8; 10:15; Ps 106:4</p> <p>Psalm 44:4 ¹Lit <i>salvation</i> ^aPs 74:12 ^bPs 42:8</p> <p>Psalm 44:5 ^aDeut 33:17; Ps 60:12; Dan 8:4 ^bPs 108:13; Zech 10:5</p> <p>Psalm 44:6 ^a1 Sam 17:47; Ps 33:16; Hos 1:7</p> <p>Psalm 44:7 ^aPs 136:24 ^bPs 53:5</p> <p>Psalm 44:8 ¹<i>Selah</i> may mean: <i>Pause, Crescendo</i> or <i>Musical interlude</i> ^aPs 34:2 ^bPs 30:12</p>	<p>Psalm 44:9 ^aPs 43:2; 60:1, 10; 74:1; 89:38; 108:11 ^bPs 69:19 ^cPs 60:10; 108:11</p> <p>Psalm 44:10 ^aLev 26:17; Josh 7:8, 12; Ps 89:43 ^bPs 89:41</p> <p>Psalm 44:11 ¹Lit <i>for food</i> ^aPs 44:22; Rom 8:36 ^bLev 26:33; Deut 4:27; 28:64; Ps 106:27; Ezek 20:23</p> <p>Psalm 44:12 ¹Lit <i>for no wealth</i> ²Or <i>set a high price on them</i> ^aDeut 32:30; Judg 2:14; 3:8; Is 52:3, 4; Jer 15:13</p> <p>Psalm 44:13 ^aDeut 28:37; Ps 79:4; 89:41 ^bPs 80:6; Ezek 23:32</p> <p>Psalm 44:14 ¹Lit <i>shaking of the head</i> ^aJob 17:6; Ps 69:11; Jer 24:9 ^b2 Kin 19:21; Ps 109:25</p> <p>Psalm 44:15 ¹Lit <i>the shame of my face has covered me</i> ^a2 Chr 32:21; Ps 69:7</p> <p>Psalm 44:16 ^aPs 74:10 ^bPs 8:2</p>
--	--

Psalm 44:17

^aPs 78:7; 119:61, 83, 109, 141, 153, 176

^bPs 78:57

Psalm 44:18

^aPs 78:57

^bJob 23:11; Ps 119:51, 157

Psalm 44:19

^aPs 51:8; 94:5

^bJob 30:29; Is 13:22; Jer 9:11

^cJob 3:5; Ps 23:4

Psalm 44:20

¹Lit *palms*

^aPs 78:11

^bDeut 6:14; Ps 81:9

Psalm 44:21

^aPs 139:1, 2; Jer 17:10

Psalm 44:22

^aRom 8:36

^bIs 53:7; Jer 12:3

Psalm 44:23

^aPs 7:6

^bPs 78:65

^cPs 77:7

Psalm 44:24

^aJob 13:24; Ps 88:14

^bPs 42:9; Lam 5:20

Psalm 44:25

^aPs 119:25

Psalm 44:26

^aPs 35:2

^bPs 6:4; 25:22

Targum

Psa. 44:1 For praise; for David, composed by the sons of Korah, good discernment. ² O LORD, with our ears we have heard, our fathers have told us of the deed you did in their days, in the days of old. ³ You drove out the Canaanite Gentiles with your mighty hand; and you planted them, the house of Israel, in their land; you broke the peoples and sent them away. ⁴ For they did not inherit the land by the strength of their swords, and the might of their arms did not redeem them, for [it was] your right hand, and your strong arm and the light of your glorious splendor; for whenever they occupied themselves with the Torah, you were pleased with them. ⁵ You are my king, O God; at this time command the redemption of the house of Jacob. ⁶ At your command we will gore our oppressors; in your name we will subdue all who rise against us. ⁷ For I do not trust in my bow, and my sword will not redeem me. ⁸ For you have redeemed us from our oppressors and from those who hate us, you have brought shame upon them. ⁹ By the word of the LORD we sing praise all day; and your name we will confess forever and ever. ¹⁰ Only you have neglected [us] and put us to shame; and your presence will not abide with our forces. ¹¹ You have made us turn our back in the presence of our enemies, and those who hate us have subdued us. ¹² You have handed us over like sheep for food, and you have scattered us among the Gentiles. ¹³ You sold your people for nothing, for no money; and you did not increase property by their exchange. ¹⁴ You have made us a disgrace to our neighbors, a mockery and scandal to our surroundings. ¹⁵ You have made us a proverb among the Gentiles, a shaking of the head among the nations. ¹⁶ All the day my disgrace is before me, and shame has covered my face. ¹⁷ From the sound of the reviler and vilifier, from the presence of the enemy and revenge-taker; ¹⁸ All this has come upon us, yet we have not neglected you, and we have not been false to your covenant. ¹⁹ We will not turn back hesitating, our hearts being proud, but you have diverted our steps from the straightness of the path. ²⁰ For you have humbled us in a place of jackals, and you have covered us with the shadow of death. ²¹ If we have neglected the name of our God and spread our hands in prayer to an idol of foreign nations – ²² Truly, God will search this out, for he knows the hidden things of the heart. ²³ For on your account we are killed all the day; we are accounted as sheep handed over for slaughter. ²⁴ Act mightily; why will you be like a sleeping man, O LORD? Arouse yourself, do not forever be forgetful. ²⁵ Why will you remove your glorious presence, why neglect our shame and oppression? ²⁶ For our soul is bent to the dust; our bowels cleave to the bottom of the pit. ²⁷ Arise, help us, and redeem us, for the sake of your goodness.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This is the third composition of the sons of Korah. It is a memoir dedicated to Eretz Israel. The Psalm describes vividly the Divine assistance which allowed Israel to conquer the land. Through the study of the Torah and the performance of the mitzvot in the Torah, Israel seized the spiritual cone of each objective in the LORD's plan. The conquest of the land can be seen as a metaphor for Israel conquering the meaning and purpose of the Torah. The Psalmist mourn the bitter defeat that came with the Babylonian Exile because the people abandoned their divine weapons (Torah study). Even in Exile, there was the hope that the LORD would allow a remnant to return to the land.

Superscript

The Psalmist commences this Psalm with a call to the Sefirah Netzach for victory. The NASB translation, along with many of the English translations, use the translation of "choir director" for the word לְמַנְצֵחַ, which is at its root Netzach.

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory

Verse one

Why does Israel have faith in the LORD? The reason is that the Jewish religion is based upon the tradition of our ancestors (fathers), who have told us of what they have experienced. They saw the great acts of the LORD to create and save the nation.

God, we have heard with our ears; our fathers have told us the work you had wrought in their days, in antiquity.

Verse two

The Psalmist gives credit to the hand of the LORD for driving the people out of the Promised Land when Joshua and Israel conquered the land. It was a divine judgment that the LORD gave to the tribes in the land that resisted Israel.

With your hand, you drove out the nations through the Sefirah Gevurah and drove them away.

Verse three

כִּי לֹא בַחַרְבָּם (key lo v'char'bam) – means “because of their swords.” The Israelites owned the possession of the land to three factors. First is that the LORD’s right hand saved them. Secondly, the LORD’s arm chastised the Canaanites. The third is the bliss inherent in the goals of Divine sovereignty.

For not by their own sword have they conquered the land, their arm has not saved them, but it was Your right hand and Your arm and the light of Your countenance because You found Your will in them.

Verse four

The Psalmist said that the LORD intervened with acts that revealed You in their early history.

You are my king, even as You are God, executing judgment. Commanding the salvation of Jacob.

Verses five & six

The Psalmist says that the LORD's aid overcame the oppressors even while Israel was in exile. Through the LORD's name, Israel's foes were driven off.

With You, we would push down our oppressors, and with Your Name, we would tread them under that which rises up against us.

For I would not put my trust in my bow, neither should my sword save me.

Verse seven

The people experienced the LORD's help while in exile in Babylon.

For You have saved us from our oppressors, and You have put to shame those who sowed hatred against us.

Verse eight

בְּאֱלֹהִים (bealohim) – means “in God.” This was the motto with which Israel has always confidently faced the future. Israel gratefully recorded every new acquisition and will always give thanks to the Name of the LORD alone forever.

In God, this was our glory all the day, and we shall give thanks to Your Name forever. Meditate on this verse.

Verse nine

During the Babylonian Exile, the Hebrew people felt that the LORD was not with them. In Exile, the Israelites prayed to the LORD, telling Him that they never forgot Him.

Even though You seemed to forget us while we were in Exile, you did make us aware of our unworthiness, and you did go out with our armies.

Verse ten

The Israelites knew that they were powerless because the LORD was not with their armies. They could not fight back. The hatred of the surrounding nations was caused by slander and because of the selfishness of those nations.

You make us turn back when an enemy appears, and those who sow hatred against us plunder us for their own gains.

Verse eleven

The Hebrew people believed that to murder a Jew, in that time, seemed no more wicked than to slaughter a sheep. The people wondered why the LORD allowed the murdering of His people to occur. Eventually, the Hebrew people were scattered and became minorities in foreign countries.

You give us up like sheep to be murdered and have scattered us among the nations.

Verse twelve

The people felt that they were like property of the LORD. The people saw how different nations conquered them to rule over them. The LORD did not earn profit by doing this. Thus, it was difficult to understand why it was happening.

You sell Your people for worthless gain and have truly had no gain from their constant exchanges.

Verse thirteen

The people around us know that our life with you, LORD is a great way to live.

You make us an object of ridicule to our neighbors, a scorn and derision to those around us.

Verse fourteen

The surrounding nations laughed at Israel.

You have made a joke around the nations, a laughingstock among the peoples.

Verses fifteen & sixteen

The nation felt that they were covered in shame.

All-day long, my dishonor is before me, and my humiliation has overwhelmed me,

Before the voice of him, that reviles and blasphemes, before the enemy and the avenger.

Verse seventeen

All that came upon Israel (verse 9-16) led the people to determine that the covenant with the LORD might have been broken.

All this came upon us, but yet we have not forgotten You; we have not been false to Your covenant.

Verses eighteen & nineteen

תַּנְיִן (tanee) – means “dragon or sea monster.” The NASB translation uses the word jackals which is incorrect.

The Psalmist uses the excuse that the breaking of the covenant from time to time was caused by the suffering of the violence against Israel. It became too much for the people.

Our hearts had not turned back, even when our steps turned away from Your path.

When You allowed us to be trodden down where dragons dwell and covered us with the shadow of death.

Verses twenty and twenty-one

When our actions demonstrated a lack of adherence to the LORD's Torah, the people never forgot the LORD. In history, the circumstances of that time forced the people to act against the LORD. It was an unfortunate time for both the LORD and Israel.

Had we forgotten the Name of our God, even when we spread forth our hands to a strange god,

Then God would search this out, for he knows the heart's secrets.

Verse twenty-two

The Psalmist said to the LORD that despite what looked like disloyalty, the people did demonstrate at times that they were killing and ready to die for the LORD like slaughtered sheep.

For it was for Your sake that we were killed all this time; we were considered sheep for the slaughter.

Verses twenty-three & twenty-four

Even though it appears that LORD, you are asleep, we still call out to your Name.

Show that You are awake; why do you wish to appear as if asleep, LORD?

Let it be a time of waking; forsake us not forever

Why do You wish to hide your countenance and forget our affliction and oppression?

Verse twenty-six

Both the LORD and Israel have lost our mental and physical power to rise again.

For our soul is bowed down to the dust; our body lies on the ground altogether.

Verse twenty-seven

The Psalmist asks the LORD to come to Israel's aid and redeem her through the Sefirah Chesed.

Arise to our aid, and redeem us through the Sefirah Chesed.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory
God, we have heard with our ears; our fathers have told us the work you had wrought in their days, in antiquity.

With your hand, you drove out the nations through the Sefirah Gevurah and drove them away.

For not by their own sword have they conquered the land, their arm has not saved them, but it was Your right hand and Your arm and the light of Your countenance because You found Your will in them.

You are my king, even as You are God, executing judgment. Commanding the salvation of Jacob.

With You, we would push down our oppressors, and with Your Name, we would tread them under that which rises up against us.

For I would not put my trust in my bow, neither should my sword save me.

For You have saved us from our oppressors, and You have put to shame those who sowed hatred against us.

In God, this was our glory all the day, and we shall give thanks to Your Name forever. Meditate on this verse.

Even though You seemed to forget us while we were in Exile, you did make us aware of our unworthiness, and you did go out with our armies.

You make us turn back when an enemy appears, and those who sow hatred against us plunder us for their own gains.

You give us up like sheep to be murdered and have scattered us among the nations.

You sell Your people for worthless gain and have truly had no gain from their constant exchanges.

You make us an object of ridicule to our neighbors, a scorn and derision to those around us.

You have made a joke around the nations, a laughingstock among the peoples.

All-day long, my dishonor is before me, and my humiliation has overwhelmed me,

Before the voice of him, that reviles and blasphemes, before the enemy and the avenger.

All this came upon us, but yet we have not forgotten You; we have not been false to Your covenant.

Our hearts had not turned back, even when our steps turned away from Your path.

When You allowed us to be trodden down where dragons dwell and covered us with the shadow of death.

Had we forgotten the Name of our God, even when we spread forth our hands to a strange god,

Then God would search this out, for he knows the heart's secrets.

Show that You are awake; why do you wish to appear as if asleep, LORD? Let it be a time of waking; forsake us not forever

Why do You wish to hide your countenance and forget our affliction and oppression?

For our soul is bowed down to the dust; our body lies on the ground altogether.

Arise to our aid, and redeem us through the Sefirah Chesed.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

